

A 3D-printed underactuated soft gripper with sensors on fingertips

Virginia Burini
Dipartimento di Ingegneria
Univeristà degli Studi di Perugia
Perugia, Italy
virginia.burini@unipg.it

Silvia Logozzo
Dipartimento di Ingegneria
Univeristà degli Studi di Perugia
Perugia, Italy
silvia.logozzo@unipg.it

Maria Cristina Valigi
Dipartimento di Ingegneria Univeristà
degli Studi di Perugia
Perugia, Italy
mariacristina.valigi@unipg.it

Abstract— *In recent years, soft robotic grippers have attracted significant attention due to their unique capabilities and sustainable impact across various scientific and industrial applications, particularly in robotic grasping and manipulation. Grasping is a delicate task that often requires both dexterity and precision to securely hold objects without causing damage. To enhance these capabilities, cost-effective, 3D-printed soft devices have been prototyped, with a focus on improving precision, robustness, and versatility. This work explores the design, characterization, and force recognition of a novel 3D-printed underactuated soft gripper, which features four monolithic soft fingers actuated by tendons and equipped with sensors on the fingertips. The sensors embedded in the fingertips are Force Sensing Resistors (FSRs), which have been characterized and calibrated to regulate grasping forces.*

Keywords— *Underactuated gripper, Force Sensing Resistor, Robotic Fingertip.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The paper presents the development and contact force recognition of the fingertip of a novel underactuated soft gripper that integrates 3D printing technology and soft robotics principles. The gripper has four tendon-actuated soft fingers, allowing adaptability for grasping various objects. Force Sensing Resistors (FSRs) are embedded in the silicone fingertips to measure and calibrate the forces during grasping. This sensor feedback enhances the gripper's precision and makes it suitable for handling delicate items. The paper also details the integration and calibration of the FSRs, improving the gripper's capabilities for many uses (Fig.1). The robotic fingertip with embedded and calibrated sensors is an important novelty in the scenario of underactuated fingers [1]. The silicone material used for the fingertips improves the gripper's compliance and contact surface area, [2-3]. The study focused on the calibration and characterization of the system to ensure accurate force detection and control. A similar gripper is in [4-5] but the sensor was only directly calibrated on the robotic fingertip without any characterization on the stand alone sensor and validation. The implementation of this sensor feedback allows for enhanced manipulation capabilities, making the soft gripper suitable for a variety of industrial, medical, and service-based applications where adaptability and safe interaction with objects are crucial [6-7].

A. Underactuated grippers: stiffness of joints and fingertips

Underactuated grippers are distinguished by having a lower number of actuators than degrees of freedom (DOFs), enabling them to adapt to the shape of the manipulated object. This property makes them particularly effective for handling objects with irregular shapes or fragile structures. Nevertheless, the potential for damage or breakage of such

objects cannot be entirely precluded. To mitigate these risks and to handle objects with specific elastic or surface characteristics, it is advantageous to incorporate force sensors and rigorously characterize the stiffness of both the fingertips and joints of the robotic fingers.

Fig. 1. The proposed underactuated gripper with the following features. The finger is equipped with embedded sensors located on the fingertip for enhanced tactile sensing (on the upper right), and the fingertip is made with silicone material to improve grip and provide a soft, adaptable contact surface for handling objects (on the lower right).

This facilitates the visualization and optimization of grasping trajectories. Utilizing a precisely designed 3D-printed tip to contact the FSR ensured complete coverage of the sensor's sensitive area, minimizing potential errors from edge effects and deformation. To achieve a stable signal, a filtering circuit was integrated with an *Arduino UNO* controller. Specifically, the signal was first amplified with an operational amplifier and then filtered through an active low-pass filter before processing by the microcontroller.

B. Force Sensing Resistor (FSR): characterization and calibration procedures

The contact force between the finger and the grasped object can be monitored in real-time by integrating a force sensor. Force Sensing Resistors (FSRs) such as Fig.2 are inexpensive sensors that measure static and dynamic forces. They have two conductive layers separated by a resistive layer; pressure reduces the resistance by bringing the conductive layers closer together. Tests revealed that accuracy was significantly compromised by two main issues: the strong dependency of output values on the force application area due to deformability, and instability of the output values, which are associated with the edge effect and passive film effect. Before using a Force Sensing Resistor (FSR) in a gripper, it is essential to perform characterization and calibration to ensure accurate measurements. The rigorous characterization

procedure aims to precisely measure the force perpendicular to the sensor's plane, considering the non-linearity of FSRs, which makes them more sensitive to low forces and less responsive to higher forces.

Fig. 2. An FSR402 (Interlink Electronics, USA) with a 14.2 mm and the circuit.

II. RESULTS

To characterize the behavior of an FSR sensor over a range of applied forces from 0 to 30 N, an IMADA ZTA-50N force gauge was used, applying forces in non-uniform steps. This approach took advantage of the sensor's non-linearity, highlighting its greater sensitivity to lower forces. Corresponding data were recorded for each applied force, with measurements repeated multiple times to compile a robust dataset. Finally, a fitting curve was identified to model the experimental data, which was then integrated with Arduino. Fig.3 shows the obtained. A generalized exponential function describes FSR characterization.

Fig. 3. FSR characterization curve characterizing the sensor

To establish a relationship between the Arduino output signal and the measured force value, calibration curves were obtained.

Fig. 4. Calibration curve obtained for the PETG fingertip

These curves enable the translation of the raw signal measurement accuracy and allowing for proper interpretation of the collected data. Experiments were conducted and calibration curves were obtained for the PETG fingertip (Fig. 4) and the PETG fingertip with the silicone element (Fig. 5). The Fig.5 shows a greater dispersion of values and a loss of repeatability,

especially at high applied force values. As a result of the implementation of the calibration curves in the controller, the validation procedure revealed an average error between -0.2 and +0.5 N for the PETG fingertip and from -0.4 to +0.9 N for the silicone fingertip.

Fig. 5. Calibration curve obtained for the silicone element

III. EXPERIMENTS

Experimental tests were carried out to find the threshold forces needed to support, deform, and break specific objects and to perform force adjustment. Fig.6 shows one of those experiments.

Fig. 6. Example of grasping experiment

REFERENCES

- [1] Achilli GM, Logozzo S, Malvezzi M, Valigi MC. (2023) Underactuated embedded constraints gripper for grasping in toxic environments. *SN Applied Sciences* 5(4): art. 96.
- [2] Logozzo S, Valigi MC, Malvezzi M. (2022) Modelling the human touch: A basic study for haptic technology. *Tribology International* 166: art. 107352K. Elissa, "Title of paper if known," unpublished.
- [3] J Low JH, Khin PM, Han QQ, Yao H, Teoh YS, Zeng Y, Li S, Liu J, Liu Z, Valdivia Y Alvarado P, Chen IM, Tee BCK, Yeow CH. (2022) Sensorized Reconfigurable Soft Robotic Gripper System for Automated Food Handling. *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics* 27(5): 3232-3243.
- [4] A.Saboukhi, M.R.Gorji, E. Amirpour, M. Savabi, R. Fesharak ifard, H. Ghafarirad, S. M. Rezaei, Design-and experimental analysis of a force sensitive gripper for safe robot applications, in: 2019 7th International Conference on Robotics and Mecha tronics (ICRoM), IEEE, 2019, pp. 345–351
- [5] . A. Matos, S. Caballa, D. Zegarra, M. A. A. Guzman, D. Lizano, D. F. G. Encinas, H. Oscanoa, D. Arce, Three-fingered grip per for multimorph object grasping with force feedback sensing control, in: 2020 IEEE ANDESCON, IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–5
- [6] Forero JD, Valencia GE, Obregón L. (2018) Methodology of calibration of FSR sensor for seat occupancy detection in vehicles. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology* 11(23).
- [7] Achilli GM, Logozzo S, Malvezzi M and Valigi MC (2022) Contact mechanics analysis of a soft robotic fingerpad. *Front. Mech. Eng* 8:966335. doi: 10.3389/fmech.2022.966335

